

**EFFECTS OF PROCESS ORIENTED GUIDED INQUIRY
LEARNING INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY ON STUDENTS’
ACHIEVEMENT AND RETENTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL
ALGEBRA IN BWARI AREA COUNCIL, ABUJA, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT: *This study examined the effects of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) instructional strategy on secondary school students’ achievement and retention of algebra in Bwari Area Council, Abuja Nigeria. Four research questions guided the study based on the four purpose of the study highlighted in the work. Four research hypothesis were also formulated and tested at an alpha level of 0.05 level of significance. The research adopted the quasi-experimental non-randomized pre and post-test control group. Data were collected from a sample of 100 students comprising 53 boys and 47 girls from two randomly selected public schools in the Bwari Area Council. The schools were grouped into experimental and control group. A 20 item instrument called Algebra Achievement Test (AAT) developed by the researcher with a reliability coefficient of 0.83 using Kuder-Richardson formula 21 was used for data collection. The AAT was administered thrice, before experiment (Pre), after experiment (Post) and two weeks after post AAT (Retention test). Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and ANCOVA at coefficient alpha level of 0.05 for testing the hypotheses. Findings of the study are; there was significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught algebra with process oriented guided inquiry learning and those taught with conventional method, there was significant difference between the retention of students taught mathematics with process oriented guided inquiry learning and those taught with conventional method and There was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics with process oriented guided inquiry learning. It was recommended that teachers in training should be trained properly on how to use Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) to teach mathematics in secondary schools.*

INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

Mathematics plays a significant role in the development of any society. It also occupies a central place in the Nigerian educational system. The position of Mathematics makes it necessary for the use of innovative pedagogical strategies that will enable teachers to meet the challenges of teaching and learning the subject especially in this era of, the information age. The development of mathematics is, without question, one of the great achievements of man due to its importance in the natural and social sciences.

The study of Mathematics fosters logical thinking, emphasizes precision in language and notation, improves pattern recognition, encourages multiple ways of looking at a particular problem, and increases one's ability to understand the complex world in which we live and helps us to make sense of our world and appeals to our senses of beauty and reason (Salami & Popoola, 2016). Hamza and Timayi (2018) pointed out that mathematics is the gate and key to science. The importance of Mathematics to nation building has led the Federal Government of Nigeria to make Mathematics a core subject to be offered by students at all levels of education in Nigeria (FRN, 2014). Anaduaka and Okafor (2013) noted that Mathematics is a compulsory subject required for entry into university education, especially for science related courses.

David (2014) regarded Mathematics as both the queen and servant of all the sciences. Undoubtedly, mathematics is the queen of

science and the language of nature. Its importance should be clear to any reasonable person. Also, the importance of mathematics studies in Nigeria has continued to generate a great deal of interest. Likewise, Adeleke (2013) stated that Mathematics is a fundamental subject which plays a cogent role in understanding and applying concepts in mathematics as well in grappling with the complexities of modern technology useful to humanity which is all about providing solutions to human problems. Ezeugwu and Igbo (2014) described mathematics as an indispensable tool in the study of sciences, humanities and technology. Mathematics is the key and backbone of almost all school subjects offered at any level of education.

Mathematics encourages the habit of self-reliance and assists learners to think and solve their problems themselves. Mathematical knowledge indeed equips individuals with the skill to solve a wide range of practical tasks and problems they may encounter in life and in vocations (Anaduaka, 2013) it's the importance of mathematics that compelled the Federal Government of Nigeria to make mathematics a compulsory subject from primary school through to the end of the senior secondary school education.

Sunday (2018) argued that mathematics is not only the language of the sciences, but an essential nutrient for thought, logical reasoning and progress. Mathematics liberates the mind and also gives individuals an assessment of their intellectual abilities by pointing towards the

direction of improvement. He concluded by saying that mathematics is the basis of all sciences and technology whose application cut across all areas of human knowledge. The essence of mathematics, therefore, lies in its beauty and its intellectual challenge. Both scientific breakthroughs and technological development are facilitated by the precise language of mathematics. This means that there is a strong link between progress in mathematics and technological advancement. Thus, every man requires a certain amount of competence in basic topics in mathematics for the purposes of handling money, prosecuting daily business, interpreting mathematical graphs and charts as well as thinking logically.

In spite of all these, the subject is still seen as a difficult one and has generated phobias among learners. The disparity in scholastic achievement of students in Nigeria has been and is still a source of concern and research interest to educators, government and parents. This is so because of the great importance it has for the national development of the country. All over the country, there is a consensus of opinion about the falling standard of education in Nigeria (Samuel, 2018).

Parents and government are in total agreement that their huge investment in education is not yielding the desired dividend. Teachers also complain of students' low performance at both internal and external examinations. Irrespective of the great importance of mathematics in nation building, scientific and technological development, it is still notable that students'

performance in mathematics at internal and external examinations has not been too impressive (See Appendix XI).

The overall performance in mathematics at the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination in Nigerian secondary schools shows that above 60% of the student obtained A1 to C6. So there is still more room for improvement. The search for explanation of some students' poor performance in schools is far from being concluded as it remains one major controversial issue in education.

From Appendix XI, the WASSCE results obtained from 2011-2016 shows that majority of the students performed poorly in mathematics. This result for those years shows that less than 50% of the students got A1 – C6. However, there was increase in the performance rate from 2017-2018, where more of the students got A1 – C6, but still this is not good enough because a whole scored below credit pass. This means that those who scored below credit pass will not be able to secure admission into the university since a credit pass in the mathematics is one of the prerequisite for that.

A great number of researchers reported that students blamed their poor performance on three broad areas: teaching problems, negative attitudes of students towards the subject, and examination difficulty. Adigun and Sam-Kayode (2018) had earlier identified problems of mathematics learning as students' perception of the same as to be highly theoretical and meaningless. The authors further observed that teachers adopt poor methods in the teaching of

mathematics in schools, and that the high percentage of the relatively small number of available textbooks does not reflect the culture of the Nigerian children. He submitted that mathematics teachers often say mathematics is useful but fail to show its usefulness. Hence, most students cannot see a reason for studying mathematics.

Akanmu (2019) opined that the search for the causation of poor academic achievement in mathematics is unending and some of the major factors they put forward are: methods of teaching, self-esteem/self-efficacy, study habits, teacher consultation and poor interpersonal relationships. This is a great source of concern considering the fact that mathematics plays a vital role in scientific, technological and social progress of any nation and indeed all works of life. The debate on appropriate teaching strategy is inclusive and widely open to further investigation. Consequently, the question emerges again. Does learning strategy affect students' performance in mathematics? To find out whether or not learning strategies affect students' performance in mathematics at secondary school level, teachers employ various instructional methods in the classroom.

According to Ebesine (2016), teaching methods are in a continuum, ranging from expository to inquiry method. The expository method of teaching is traditional and widely used in the classroom. Muhammad and Purwanto, (2020) also reported the characteristics of the expository method to include the following: Learner-centered, leader-active, learner-passive and

content emphasis. Examples of the expository method are lectures, discussion, traditional demonstration, guest speaker, panel discussion, story taking, dramatization and reading of textbooks, manuals or handouts.

The inquiry method is an approach where the learner generates his/her own form of information. It is characterized by the following features: learner- centered, leader-facilitated, learner-active, and learning process emphasis. In general, the expository method of teaching is considered to be leader-centered with an emphasis on content delivery, while the inquiry method is considered learner-centered with an emphasis on the process of learning. In a typical learning situation, the leader is actively involved in the expository method of instruction. Example, the leader or teacher engages in lecturing, reading aloud, and showing a video) and the learner is passively taking in the information (for example, listening, reading an overhead, watching a video). In contrast, learners who engage in inquiry are actively involved (for example, conducting investigations, processing information and data) while the leader's role is to help facilitate the process of learning (Hossain, 2018). Examples of inquiry methods are process oriented-guided inquiry lessons, cooperative learning, guided discovery, problem solving and inquiry methods. This study investigated the effect of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) and Traditional Approaches on students' achievement in secondary school Algebraic Mathematics.

Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) is a research-based, student-centered philosophy and science pedagogy in which students work in small groups to engage in guided inquiry using carefully designed materials that direct and guide students to build and rebuild their knowledge (Walker and Warfa 2017; Muhammad and Purwanto, 2020). This simultaneously teaches both content and key process skills of science. POGIL activities focus on core concepts and processes of science as it encourages and fosters a deep understanding of the course material while developing higher-order thinking skills. Process-oriented guided inquiry lesson is a method of learning that has the advantage of allowing learners to use process skills to generate content information. It actively engages learners in first-hand real world learning. It encourages learners to explore the content through the use of concrete experiences. Teachers are released from the role of authority and they become facilitators and fellow investigators. This replaces the notion that the teacher must know all the answers.

POGIL is a powerful instructional approach that guides and motivates learners to explore information and concepts in order to construct new ideas, identify new relationships and create new models of thinking and behaviour (Muhammad & Purwanto, 2020). The teacher has to be sure about the reason for applying POGIL. Learning educational materials in POGIL sessions are highly experimental and interactive. They make use of stories, games, simulations, visual maps and other techniques to

get attention, build interest and lead learners on a journey of discovery towards new thinking, actions and behaviour. The POGIL approach incorporates three key models: Problem solving: The learning design must guide and motivate learners to participate in problem solving as they pull together information and generalized knowledge. Learner management: Learning must be learner-driven so that participants, working alone or in small teams, can learn at their own pace. Integrating and connecting: Learning must encourage the integration of new knowledge into the learners' existing knowledge and clearly connect to the real world (Moog, 2014).

In contrast, the traditional classroom often looks like a one-person show with a largely uninvolved learner. Traditional classes are usually dominated by direct and unilateral instruction. Traditional approach followers assume that there is a fixed body of knowledge that the student must come to know. Students are expected to blindly accept the information they are given without questioning the instructor (Ahmed, 2016). The teacher seeks to transfer thoughts and meanings to the passive student, leaving little room for student-initiated questions, independent thought or interaction between students (Nwafor, Ibrahim and Ambrose, 2018). Even in activity-based subjects, although activities are done in a group, they do not encourage discussion or exploration of the concepts involved. This tends to overlook the critical thinking and unifying concepts essential to true science literacy and appreciation

(Nwafor, et al., 2018). This teacher-centered method of teaching also assumes that all students have the same level of background knowledge in the subject and are able to absorb the material at the same pace (Lord, et al., 2012). The major is how to get mathematics teachers to depart from the traditional method of teaching and integrate approaches into an active learning approach. The effectiveness of the mathematics teachers depends on their consideration of the nature of the subject during instructional planning. Mathematics is not a subject that can be mastered by mere memorization of basic rules. It requires total involvement of the learner in the learning process, sound theoretical knowledge and intensive practice in the application of basic principles. The extent to which mathematics teachers involve these principles goes a long way in helping students understand Algebra, which is the foundation of mathematics.

Algebra is a branch of mathematics which treats the relations and properties of quantities by means of letters and other symbols. It is applicable to those relations that are true of every kind of magnitude. (Merriam-website, 2025). Algebra uses mathematical statements to describe relationships between things that vary. These variables include things like the relationship between the supply of an object and its price. When we use a mathematical statement to describe a relationship, we often use letters to represent the quantity that varies, since it is not a fixed number.

According to Olorunishola (2023), males and

females are gifted at academic achievement and none is superior to the other. Besides, Sunday (2018) stated that males in junior and senior secondary schools like mathematics better than female students do. It appears that findings on gender as a factor in mathematics achievement are contradictory.

Retention ability is another factor that influences performance of students in mathematics. Ezeamenyi (2014) asserts that failure to provide enough application of contents learnt to real life activities, social usage and poor teaching techniques are strong limiting factors to students' retention in mathematics. Retention refers to the ability to remember or utilize already acquired knowledge or skills. It is the capacity to remember something, skills, knowledge, habits, attitudes or other responses initially acquired. Retention plays an important role for what is learnt to be effectively applied. Owing to the interplay of these variables this study is designed to investigate the effect of Process Oriented Guided inquiry Learning (POGIL) and traditional approaches on students' achievement in secondary school algebra mathematics.

Statement of the Problem

Mathematics is literally necessary in every field of human endeavor. It plays a fundamental role in educational advancement. This is seen in all the technological advancement in the world today, which is because of scientific investigations. However, the issue remains that in most secondary schools in Nigeria, there is a high rate of failure in the subject (See Appendix

J). This study focuses on Bwari Area Council a densely populated area comprising people from diverse part of Nigeria making it a representative setting. The low performance of students in examinations in mathematics has been traced to the lack of interest of students in mathematics. Our aspiration towards scientific and technological advancement is the propelling force that we need nothing short of good achievement in mathematics at all levels of schooling. Since education started from the home, one would wonder why there is a great increase in mass failure in mathematics with the number of instructors, facilitators, educators, educationists, teachers, and academics in this nation. The phobia of mathematics as a subject has driven a large number of students from putting enough ability into the discovery of the subject to about creating false impressions about mathematics on their own. In addition, the poor performance of students is a great challenge and concern to those in the field of mathematics, educators, physicists, and psychologists, among others. It would be enough to ask the question, are trained teachers in mathematics not the right people required to cause the desired change of performance in students? Or is there any best method to use in improving mathematical knowledge on the student? It is necessary to look deeply into the cause of this problem and proffer a solution to it. It is because of these challenges that this work examined the effect of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) on students' achievement and retention in senior secondary school algebra in Bwari Area Council.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) on students' achievement and retention in secondary school Algebra. Specifically, the study was designed to find out if:

- i. there is any difference in the mean achievement score of students taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional methods.
- ii. there is any difference in the mean retention score of students taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional methods.
- iii. there is any difference between the achievement of male and female students taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL),
- iv. there is any difference between the retention scores of male and female students taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL).

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement score of students taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional methods?
2. What is the difference in the mean retention score of students taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning

(POGIL) and those taught with conventional methods?

3. What is the different in the mean achievement scores of male and female students who were taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL)?

4. What is the different in the mean retention scores of male and female students who were taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL)?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at an alpha level of 0.05 level of significance.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of students taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional methods.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

The conceptual framework of this study illustrates the interrelationships between the

(POGIL) and those taught with conventional methods.

HO₃: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL).

HO₄: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

This chapter presents a review of related literature under the following subheadings: Theoretical framework, Conceptual framework, Review of previous studies and Summary.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework covered in this study were concept of teaching, concept of POGIL method of instruction, student academic achievements in mathematics, retention in mathematics, concept of gender.

teaching and learning of mathematics and the use of the POGIL (Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning) method of instruction. The POGIL approach serves as the central instructional strategy designed to actively engage students in the learning process. Through this method, the study explores its impact on students' achievement and retention in mathematics. Furthermore, the framework considers gender as a moderating variable, potentially influencing the outcomes of achievement and retention. Altogether, this model underscores a structured pathway through which innovative teaching strategies like POGIL can enhance mathematics education outcomes, while accounting for gender-based differences in student responses and performance.

Student Academic Achievements in Mathematics: Achievement can be seen as behaviour shown at the end of a given period of time or after a certain range. Achievement is a criterion behaviour involving the determination of characteristics of students performance with respect to certain standards.

Retention in Mathematics: Retention is the act of retaining or absorbing and holding facts on things learned. Retention, as a variable is the ability to remember things, task or material learned previously. It is the endurance of behavior, which have been learned or acquired when the behavior is not being utilized. Ezeamenyi (2014) has asserted that failure to provide enough applications to real life activity and social usage cum poor teaching techniques

are strong limiting factors to students' retention in Mathematics. He contended that for the improvement of retention of learned materials in Mathematics, activity-based learning is indispensable.

Gender: Gender which is referred to as socially determined differences between woman and man are learned and vary across cultures and overtime. Gender is a relational term that includes both woman and man. Gender equality focuses on changes for both man and woman (Vale, 2016). Gender interacts with other variables such as class, ethnicity and religion. It is the social construction of men's and women's roles in a given culture or location. Gender roles are distinguished from sex roles, which are biologically determined.

Algebra in Mathematics: Algebra is a branch of mathematics in which arithmetic operations and other formal manipulations are applied to abstract symbols rather than specific numbers (britannica.com).

Conceptual Analysis

This is where the definitions and descriptions of the various concepts under study are explained.

The Concept of Teaching

The concept of teaching is as old as man's teaching is given different definitions and interpretations by different authors. Teaching is a rational and organized process of transmitting knowledge, attitude and skills. In accordance with professional principles. It is a process of admitting or introducing someone to acquire new knowledge. According to Jordan, et al. 2008, teaching is a process leading to relatively

permanent change in behaviour. Adetute (2000) opined that teaching is training, tutorial, instructing and outright brain washing. He maintained that it is a group oriented activity carried out in formal institutions recognized as schools. Orji (2007) opined that teaching consists of services of activities that one engages in and is able to bring about desirable change in the behaviour of the learner. Teaching is an attempt to assist other people to acquire or change some skills, attitude, ideas and knowledge and help appreciate tearing. Teaching is a complex process of helping one to increase or acquire knowledge and facts. Teaching, according to (Bakkenes et al., 2010), is a purposeful interaction between a teacher and a learner resulting in a permanent change in behaviour. Teacher as we know helps to make a society what it is. The teacher performs the act of teaching and in the process influences the students.

The influence of teachers is a long good-lasting one and good teaching can make a society better, while bad teaching can harm it seriously. The influence of the teacher on the future personal, social and productive lives of pupils relies to a great extent on the professional training he received and the exposure and experiences he acquired in life So the teacher is very important in an education system because the destiny of any nation lies in the hands of those who guide its youth.

Characteristics of a Good Teacher

In a good teaching, the teacher structures his teaching in relation to:

- a. His student by being sensitive to their abilities interests and needs.
- b. The curriculum by being thoroughly familiar with what he is required to teach by helping his pupils to make sense of their work, encouraging the creative abilities of each student, helping children to develop emotionally and socially.
- c. Resource that is readily available inside or outside the school and can be handled conveniently.
- d. Teaching method that;
 - i. builds on a foundation of knowledge already possessed by the student and encourages them to learn by doing.
 - ii. ensures that learning grows out of useful experience and experimentation.
 - iii. creates a good learning environment, stimulates appreciation as well as cognitive development.
 - iv. varies the grouping of students to get the most efficient learning units for each type of lesson (Mankilik & Connie-Ofodile, 2015). The teacher achieves such structuring of his teaching by adopting different and appropriate teaching methods of instructions.

POGIL Method of Instruction

POGIL is an acronym for process oriented Guided Inquiry Learning. POGIL is a student-centered group learning instructional strategy and philosophy development through research on how students learn best. Process oriented guided inquiry lesson is a method of learning that has the advantages of allowing learners to use process skills to generate content information. It actively engages learners in first-hand real-world

learning. It encourages learners to explore the content through the use of concrete experiences. Teachers are released from the role of authority and to become facilitators and fellow investigators. It is an instructional approach combining guided inquiry and cooperative learning in which students are involved in the learning process. This replaces the notion that the teacher must know all the answers.

In a POGIL classroom, students work in small groups with different roles. It allows the students work on specially designed activities that promote mastery of discipline content and the development of skills in the processes of learning, thinking, problem solving, communication, teamwork, management, and assessment (Brown, 2010). The POGIL activities follow a learning cycle. First, students explore a model or data to find trends or patterns and generate and test hypotheses to help understand or explain the data. Then, students define or invent a new concept using the trends or patterns. Lastly, students apply the new concept in other contexts to help generalize its meaning and applicability (Kusmaul, 2012). The groups are working on worksheets that allow students to formulate the concept on the basis of what the students learned from the data, diagrams and illustrations presented (Bunce, Vandenplas, Neiles and Flens 2010).

The key components of POGIL worksheet include a descriptive title, models which can be a data or figures for students' exploration, questions to promote concept development, exercises for practice, and problems to apply the

concepts (Hanson, 2015). The sequence of key questions is used to guide the teams through inquiry process. Key questions include direct questions, convergent questions and divergent questions. It is a learning approach that was pioneered in chemistry (Minder Hout and Loertcher, 2007). The POGIL approach seeks to bridge the gap between concept and understanding by providing an innovative classroom and teaching model that allows students to work together to develop and construct important concepts of science, mathematics and other disciplines, as well as cultivate lifelong learning skills. The goal of the POGIL approach is not only to develop content mastery through students' construction of their own understanding, but also to enhance important learning skills such as information processing and written communication, critical thinking, problem solving and met cognition. Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning allows students not to simply learn material, but to discover and understand fundamental concepts about the subject and about themselves as learners.

POGIL is an evolved form of student focused effective learning (SFEL) that gives students the chance to be involved in their learning by interacting with other learners (Spencer, 1999). In his works, Spencer stressed the need to change the conventional roles of teachers and students for the successful carrying out of SFEL in students' academic achievement. According to Spencer, students are active and interested in learning when they participate in the learning.

POGIL tries to develop learning and process skills while guiding the students to an understanding of the concept.

The objectives of POGIL as outlined by Hanson (2004) are to:

- i. Develop process skills in the area of learning thinking and problem solving
- ii. Engage students to take ownership of learning
- iii. Increase students - students and students-instructor interactions
- iv. Improve attitudes toward science
- v. Foster supporting process skill teamwork, communication management and assessments that are essential for the work place

Process-Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL)

Process-Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) is a widely used active learning approach that was pioneered in Chemistry (Minderhout and Loertcher, 2007). POGIL involves creating an environment in which students are actively engaged in mastering a discipline and developing essential skills by working in self-managed teams on guided inquiry activities (Spencer, 1999; Hanson and Wolfskill, 2000).

Characteristic of POGIL

The POGIL activities contain a number of models that the students explore to answer critical thinking questions (Brown, 2010). The models may include text, equations, diagrams, tables, graphs, and figures related to the chosen concepts. Writers of POGIL activities (Luxford, Crowder, & Bretz, 2011; Spencer & Moog, 2008) usually focus on the development of one of three

concepts. The students are asked to answer some key questions, usually, sentence completion items, manipulation of physical objects, and filling in tables through which they are guided to the desired concepts. The critical thinking questions in the activity sheets test the ability of the students to apply their conceptual knowledge in new learning situations. Interpretation of graphs and written communications are ideally considered the key process skills. The POGIL activities, which are designed for upper level university courses, emphasize the exercise of a set of process skills for insightful conceptual understanding.

According to Geiger (2010), the structured POGIL activities lead to higher levels of Bloom's taxonomy, particularly at Level 2 (concept development) and Level 3 (application of knowledge to new contexts). The POGIL activities are broadly of two categories based on the learning cycle approach: concept invention activity, and concept formation activity. Concept invention (Spencer, 1999) activities typically follow the learning cycle approach of exploration, concept invention/introduction and application. In situations where the learning cycle structure is not applicable, the learning content provides opportunities for the development of process skills (Bauer and Cole, 2012).

In concept formation activities; the concept or concepts to be understood are presented in the model as a graph or table at the start of the activity. For concept formation activities, the learning cycle approach starts with the concept

introduction/concept invention stage, followed by exploration and application stages. The critical thinking questions affirm understanding of concepts presented and develop process skills. Content learning objectives are in the form of statements of what students will be able to 'gain' as a result of completing the POGIL task (Bauer and Cole, 2012).

In an article on their implementation of lecture-free biochemistry using POGIL, Minderhout and Loertscher (2007) listed four expected learning outcomes of a POGIL activity on enzyme catalysis. The structure of the POGIL activities included a pre-activity assignment, a classroom activity, and a post-activity skill exercise. In another study, Luxford, Crowder and Bretz (2011) reported that POGIL activity on symmetry elements and symmetry operations allowed students to explore and understand the concepts and helped them create definitions of common symmetry terms. The activities consisted of two models where critical thinking and exercise questions were included. During their POGIL implementation at an urban university, Ruder and Hunnicutt (2008) used POGIL class activities containing many short models with three to ten critical thinking questions each to enable the large class to stay on task and for easy intervention. The POGIL materials and the classroom facilitation support the development of both cognitive inquiry skills and group process skills (POGIL Project, 2008).

A hierarchical rating scheme in the form of rubrics (Stevens & Levi, 2005) was proposed by Bauer and Cole (2012) to provide guidance for

the development of new materials for POGIL. The POGIL rubric, according to Bauer and Cole, guides authors of POGIL activities on the intended structure to reflect the simultaneous development of inquiry and process skills.

Several POGIL practitioners (Geiger, 2010; Luxford et al., 2011) have established examples of POGIL implementation strategies in small and large enrolment chemistry classes. In a typical POGIL class, the students organize themselves into small groups of three to four. The instructors offer a structured or flexible group membership. As the students arrive for the class, the instructor projects the day's intended learning objectives and the first model of the POGIL activity. The introduction lasts a very short time, maybe a minute or two. The students are asked to explore the model and answer the questions given on the activity sheet. As the students work in groups, the instructor walks around observing the students' progress and provides directions, if sought by any student groups, without divulging any answers. This learning cycle approach of POGIL activities helps the students to identify the concepts themselves and to construct their own understanding of the concepts.

The instructor projects a series of multiple-choice clicker questions at key intervals to help groups progress towards completion and to check their understanding of the material. The students then answer the questions using a physical clicker device in about 30 seconds. Based on the results, the instructor may give a mini-lecture or a whole-class discussion to resolve any students' misunderstandings of the

concepts. This instructional method motivates students to stay engaged in their group work. In some POGIL classes, the honours students act as teaching assistants and they report back to the lecturer on any difficulties faced by the students and their progress in a particular activity. In practice, these POGIL sessions last for about 45 to 50 minutes. The class ends with a wrap-up of concepts, either with a mini-lecture or with clicker questions.

Furthermore, the students are expected to complete the exercises and/or problems as homework or complete them during the tutorial sessions. Drossman et al. (2011) assessed the mentoring programme in a first year atmospheric science class wherein four mentors developed and tested the effectiveness of a POGIL-based curriculum and reported that the use of POGIL assignments promoted graduate students' understanding of cognitive and social constructivist principles. In their qualitative studies, the mentors acknowledged the use of teamwork and student collaboration in POGIL lessons as tools to develop problem-solving skills and connect classroom topics with real life experiences. The study also reported an improved understanding of the concepts of atmospheric physics by the students with the use of well-structured POGIL assignments.

How POGIL Works

POGIL is a method that uses highly structured group sessions where students work on process-oriented tasks to derive answers as a group. The students work together in groups of three or four and are assigned one of the following roles:

Manager, Recorder, Presenter or Reflector (optional). The use of roles enforces accountability within the groups, so the outcomes are peer-driven as opposed to instructor-driven where the motivation for completing tasks is to satisfy the instructor. Each role is dependent on the other roles, so students are accountable to their peers for the function they play (Hanson & Wolfskill, 2000; Hanson, 2006; POGIL, 2012). The Manager ensures that team members are fulfilling their roles, accomplishing the assigned tasks on time, and all group members are participating in the activities and understanding the concepts. The Recorder scribes the group's discussions and important aspects of the group's observations, insights and the significant concepts learnt. The presenter delivers concise oral reports to the class. The Reflector observes group dynamics, behaviour and performance and may report to the group (or the class) about how well the group operates. The POGIL activities focus on core concepts and encourage a deep understanding of the course material through exploration to construct understanding while developing higher-order thinking skills. The tasks include directed, convergent or divergent questions. Directed questions can be answered directly from the information provided, convergent questions require groups to reach a consensus about the solution and divergent questions can have a range of possible correct responses.

To initiate POGIL in a subject, the class must first undergo a "building the POGIL culture". This is a process whereby the students come to

understand the benefits of using POGIL. This is achieved through fun exercises that prove through students effectively to students the advantages of shared information and collaborative learning. The students also learn the rules and roles of the "highly structured" group session, and the expectations for each session. Once the POGIL culture has been established, students come to class prepared for POGIL group work. While there are numerous formats for how POGIL lessons can be structured, a common approach is to have a ten minute "mini-lecture", then a "breakaway POGIL session" for five minutes. During the POGIL session, the students will work on an exercise related directly to the lecture content. The instructor mingles amongst the groups to gauge how the students are performing. At the end of the session, two or more groups are called on to report back to the class (during a "consolidation session"). The instructor then typically recaps and/or adds to the students' answers. Implementation of POGIL with no specified/required approach for its implementation, POGIL can be implemented in various ways.

It is important to note that POGIL settings are peculiar to each institution or course. Every implementation of POGIL is unique because every instructor and institutional setting is unique (POGIL Project, 2008a). However, the most common features of any POGIL classroom implementation include a daily quiz to encourage students to prepare for and attend every class, graded homework, time investment in structuring and emphasizing group work,

encouraging students to adhere to the group roles, use of facilitation strategies to promote group members' interaction, and mini-lectures. However, the uniqueness of POGIL implementations is characterized by small groups of students working collaboratively on learning cycle-oriented POGIL worksheets facilitated by instructors in a non-lecturing learning environment.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design adopted for this study was quasi-experimental non randomized pre and post-test control group (Creswell, 2009).

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises of all the senior secondary school students in Bwari Area Council.

The target population that was used for this study comprises of all Senior Secondary School (SS2) students in public Secondary School in Bwari Area Council, F C T Abuja. SS 2 students is preferred because they are not new in the system.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The sample size for this study consists of all the SS 2 students in the intact classes of the senior secondary school in Bwari Area Council of FCT Abuja.

Random sampling technique was used to select two (2) schools for the study. A total number of 100 students from SS 2 in the two (2) selected schools that constitute the sample for the study. The researcher uses fifty-three (53) students for experimental group, that is twenty-eight (28) males and twenty-five (25) females. The control group was forty-seven (47) students which

comprises of twenty-five (25) males and twenty-two (22) females

Instrumentation

The researcher uses the following instruments to collect data for the research work.

Algebra Achievement Test (AAT)

Retention Algebra Achievement Test (RAAT). This was administered to the students at the end of the experiment to collect data on students’ retention in Algebra mathematics

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The Algebra Achievement Test (AAT) was content validated with the use of a Table of Specification in constructing the test items. It was also face-validated by four Mathematics

Presentation of Data

Demographic Data

The following table indicates the percentages and numbers of respondents.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Group

Group	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Experimental Group(POGIL)	53	53
Control Group (Conventional)	47	47
Total	100	100

Table 3 shows that fifty- three respondents, representing 53%, were in the experimental group while forty-seven respondents

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Group	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	53	53
Female	47	47
Total	100	100

Table 4 shows that fifty-three respondents representing 53% were male students while

teachers as well as experts in Mathematics Education, Department of Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja. The Kuder-Richardson (KR- 21) formula was used to ascertain the internal consistency or reliability of the AAT. The value of ‘r’ was found to be 0.83.

RESULTS

Introduction

In this chapter, the data for the study were analyzed and results presented in line with the study hypotheses earlier stated. Firstly, descriptive statistics of frequency counts, mean, standard deviation, and mean gains were computed. Later, ANCOVA was used to test all the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant.

representing 47 % of the sample, were in the control group. The total sample of the study was one hundred.

forty-seven respondents, representing 47% of the sample were female students.

Equivalence of the Sample Subjects in the Groups

The equivalence of the sample subjects in the two groups in respect of achievement were

Table 3: Two-tailed t-Test Result in Respect of Pretest Mean Achievement Score Between of Experimental Group (POGIL) and the Control Group (Conventional).

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	tvalue	Std Error	Sig.@0.05	Decision
Exp.	53	16.60	4.03	98	0.648	0.762	0.119	Not Significant
Control	47	16.85	3.53					

Results on Table 5 showed that there was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of experimental group and the control group ($t=0.648$, $df=98$, $P > 0.05$). In other words, students in the two groups did not differ significantly in their pretest achievement, therefore students were assumed to be equivalent.

Data Analysis and Results

Answer to Research Questions

The answers to questions that sought to establish

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics Showing Experimental Group (POGIL) and Control Group Achievement in the Pretest and Post test

Method	Pre-test			Post-test		
	N	X	SD	X	SD	
POGIL	53	16.60	4.03	67.74	8.95	
Conventional	47	16.85	3.53	57.87	5.20	
Mean Difference		0.25		9.87		

Table 6 reveals that at pretest mean score of students in achievement score of both experimental (POGIL) and control group are 16.60 and 16.85 while the standard deviations

established through the analysis of their pretest scores using t- test statistical technique as shown in Table 5.

the possible differences in achievement among the various groups are hereby presented using frequencies, mean and standard deviation.

Research Question One: What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional method?

are 4.03 and 3.53 respectively. The mean difference of both groups is 0.25 this means that the students in experimental and control groups have similar achievement (negligible difference)

before the commencement of the experiment. At the post test mean score of students in experimental group (POGIL) is 67.74 and standard deviation is 8.95 while the control group has the mean score of 57.87 and standard deviation of 5.20. The mean difference of 9.87 in favor of experimental group over control group is an indication that the students in the

experimental group performed better than the students in the control group.

Research Question Two: What is the difference in the mean retention scores of students taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional method?

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics Showing Effect of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) on Gender Achievement in the Retention Test Scores

Method	Pre-test			Retention test		
	N	X $\bar{}$	SD	X $\bar{}$	SD	
POGIL	53	16.60	4.03	57.81	10.45	
Conventional	47	16.85	3.53	54.55	8.84	
Mean Difference		0.25		3.26		

Table 7 reveals that at pretest mean score of students in achievement score of both experimental (POGIL) and control group are 16.60 and 16.85 while the standard deviations are 4.03 and 3.53 respectively. The mean difference of both groups is 0.25 this means that the students in experimental and control groups have similar achievement (negligible difference) before the commencement of the experiment. At the retention level the students taught with POGIL method had a mean score of 57.81 with a

standard deviation of 10.45 while the students taught with conventional method had a mean score of 54.55 with a standard deviation of 8.84. In other words, the students taught with POGIL had a higher retention mean score, than those taught with conventional.

Research Question Three: What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students who were taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) differ?

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics Showing Effect of Process Oriented Guided Learning (POGIL) on Gender Achievement in the Post Test Scores

Method	Pre-test			Post test		
	N	X $\bar{}$	SD	X $\bar{}$	SD	

Male	28	17.29	3.62	70.50	8.92
Female	25	16.84	4.40	64.64	8.06
Mean Difference		0.45		5.85	

Table 8 reveals that at pretest mean score of students in achievement score of both male and female students in experimental (POGIL) are 17.29 and 16.84 while the standard deviations are 3.62 and 4.40 respectively. The mean difference of both male and female groups is 0.45 this means that both male and female students in experimental have similar achievement (negligible difference) before the commencement of the experiment. At the post test the male students had a mean score of 70.50

with a standard deviation of 8.92 while the female students had a mean score of 64.64 with a standard deviation of 8.06. In other words, the male students had a higher mean score of 5.85 than their male counterparts when exposed to algebra with process oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL).

Research Question Four: what is the difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL)?

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics Showing Effect of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning Retention on Gender in the Retention Scores

Method	Pre-test			Post test		
	N	X̄	SD	X̄	SD	
Male	28	17.29	3.62	58.71	12.13	
Female	25	16.84	4.40	56.80	8.33	
Mean Difference		0.45		1.91		

Table 9 reveals that at pretest mean score of students in achievement score of both male and female students in experimental (POGIL) are 17.29 and 16.84 while the standard deviations are 3.62 and 4.40 respectively. The mean difference of both male and female groups is 0.45 this means that both male and female students in experimental have similar achievement (negligible difference) before the commencement of the experiment. At the

retention level the male students had a mean score of 58.71 with a standard deviation of 12.13 while the female students had a mean score of 56.80 with a standard deviation of 8.33. The male students had a higher retention mean score of 1.91 than their female counterparts when exposed to algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL). In other words the mean difference in the mean retention score is 1.46

Testing of Hypotheses

The findings of the research hypotheses revealed the following;

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the

Table 8: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students taught Algebra with POGIL and Conventional Method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	3046.251 ^a	4	761.563	15.133	.000
Intercept	19539.982	1	19539.982	388.286	.000
PRETST	12.644	1	12.644	.251	.617
GROUP	2259.989	1	2259.989	44.909	.000
GENDER	31.749	1	31.749	.631	.429
GROUP * GENDER	574.761	1	574.761	11.421	.001
Error	4780.749	95	50.324		
Total	405988.000	100			
Corrected Total	7827.000	99			

a. R Squared = .389 (Adjusted R Squared = .363)

Table 10 shows that teaching method as a main factor has significant effect on students' achievement in algebra. This is because, from the table, method is significant at p-value of 0.000 and therefore at a higher p-value of 0.05, teaching method is also significant. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean achievement score of students taught algebra with process

Table 9: ANCOVA of the Difference in Retention Mean Scores of Students Taught with Algebra with POGIL and those Taught with Conventional method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
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mean achievement score of students taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional method.

oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional methods. This means that the method of teaching mathematics has a significant influence in the achievement score of students.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional method.

Corrected Model	677.856 ^a	4	169.464	1.816	.132
Intercept	13950.551	1	13950.55	149.47	.000
			1	6	
PRETEST	16.865	1	16.865	.181	.672
GROUP	232.663	1	232.663	2.493	.000
GENDER	80.811	1	80.811	.866	.354
GROUP * GENDER	307.778	1	307.778	3.298	.073
Error	8866.304	95	93.330		
Total	326288.000	100			
Corrected Total	9544.160	99			

a. R Squared = .071 (Adjusted R Squared = .032)

Table 11 shows that teaching method as a main factor has significant effect on retention of students' Algebra Achievement Test. This is because, from the table, method is significant at p-value of 0.000 and therefore at a higher p-value of 0.05, teaching method is also significant. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean retention score of students taught algebra with Process

Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) and those taught with convectional method. The above result shows that the level of students retention in mathematics in highly influenced by the teaching strategy the students were exposed to.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students' taught with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL).

Table 10: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students taught Algebra with POGIL and Conventional Method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	3046.251 ^a	4	761.563	15.133	.000
Intercept	19539.982	1	19539.982	388.28	.000
				6	
PRETST	12.644	1	12.644	.251	.617
GROUP	2259.989	1	2259.989	44.909	.000
GENDER	31.749	1	31.749	.631	.429
GROUP * GENDER	574.761	1	574.761	11.421	.001
Error	4780.749	95	50.324		
Total	405988.000	100			

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Corrected Total **7827.000** **99**

a. R Squared = .389 (Adjusted R Squared = .363)

Table 12 shows that the computed F - ratio for the effect of gender on academic performance of students in the Algebra Achievement Test was 0.631 which was not significant at P-value of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant effect of gender on the achievement performance

Table 11: ANCOVA of the Difference in Retention Mean Scores of Students Taught with Algebra with POGIL and those Taught with Conventional method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	677.856 ^a	4	169.464	1.816	.132
Intercept	13950.551	1	13950.551	149.476	.000
PRETEST	16.865	1	16.865	.181	.672
GROUP	232.663	1	232.663	2.493	.000
GENDER	80.811	1	80.811	.866	.354
GROUP * GENDER	307.778	1	307.778	3.298	.073
Error	8866.304	95	93.330		
Total	326288.000	100			
Corrected Total	9544.160	99			

a. R Squared = .071 (Adjusted R Squared = .032)

Table 13 shows that the computed F - ratio for the effect of gender on academic performance of students in the Algebra Achievement Test was 0.866 which were not significant at P-value of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant

of students in Algebra was accepted.

HO4: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL). This shows that students achievement is not affected by gender

difference in the mean retention score of male and female students taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) was accepted. This shows that the students retention scores in mathematics is not affected by gender.

Summary of Findings

The findings of this study were as follows:

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1. There is significant difference in the mean achievement score of students taught algebra with process oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional methods.

2. There is significant difference in the mean retention score of students taught algebra with process oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) and those taught with conventional methods

3. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL).

4. There is no significant difference in the mean retention score of male and female students taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL).

Discussion of Findings

The main purpose of the study was to find out the effect of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) on Students' Achievement and Retention in Senior Secondary School Algebra in Bwari area council of Federal Capital Territory, FCT Abuja. Four research questions and four hypotheses were raised to guide the study.

The data presented in Table 6 provides answer to research question one; findings revealed that the experimental group (POGIL) had a mean score of 67.74 with a standard deviation of 8.94 while those in the control group had a mean score of 57.87 with a standard deviation of 5.20. This indicates that students in the experimental group had a higher mean score than their counterparts

in the control group. The result of ANCOVA as reported in Table 10 showed that there was a statistically significant difference between mean achievements of students exposed to algebra through process oriented guided inquiry learning than those exposed to conventional method. The success of the experimental group is due to the fact that the process oriented guided inquiry learning students work in small groups with different roles and this allows the students work on specially designed activities that promote mastery of discipline content and the development of skills in the processes of learning, thinking, problem solving, communication, teamwork, management, and assessment. This is in line with the findings of Şenol, Ayhan and Ömer (2015) that POGIL improved students' mastery approach, task value, control of learning beliefs, self-efficacy for learning and performance, critical thinking, help seeking, peer learning, meta-cognitive self-regulation, effort regulation, time/study environmental management. The results showed that POGIL was superior to the traditionally designed chemistry instruction on students' self-regulated learning skills. Thus, POGIL is helpful for development of students' self-regulated learning skills.

The data presented in Table 7 provide answer to research question two; findings revealed that the retention of students in experimental group (POGIL) had a mean score of 57.81 with a standard deviation of 10.45 while those in the control group had a mean score of 54.55 with a standard deviation of 8.84. This indicates the

retention of students in the experimental group had a higher mean score than their counterparts in the control group. The result of ANCOVA as reported in Table 11 showed that there was significant difference between the retention of students taught algebra through process oriented guided inquiry learning and those taught with conventional method.

This finding shows that retention ability level of students in both group decline but that of process oriented guided inquiry learning decline more than that of conventional method. This confirm Isah and Galadim (2023) that students taught with cooperative learning strategies performed and retained significantly higher than students taught with cooperative learning strategies. This finding is also in line with Osakwe, Egara, Inweregbugh, Nzeadibe and Emefo (2023) students taught geometric construction utilizing interaction patterns remembered more material than those taught using the expository approach. Several reasons may be the cause of the decline, including not linking content activities to the context often learning cycle may at one point not fully remember after some times, exhaustion from the unit being twice as long as other units. The data presented in Table 8 provide answer to research question three; finding revealed that in experimental group male students had a mean score of 70.50 with a standard deviation of 8.92 while the female students had a mean score of 64.64 with a standard deviation of 8.06. In other words, the male students had a higher mean score than their female counterparts. The result of ANCOVA as reported in Table 12 revealed that

there was no statistically significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to algebra with process oriented guided inquiry learning. On the achievement between male and female students, the results showed that male students achieved higher than their female counterparts. The higher achievement of the male could be due to the fact students explore a model or data to find trends or patterns and generate and test hypotheses to help understand or explain the data more than female students. This result concurred with the findings of Marcel Papka Agah (2020) There was no significant gender difference in the students taught mathematics using Cooperative learning strategy in the study area. These findings contribute significant implications for the enhancement of scientific thinking skills among various students' capabilities and different categories of school. The data presented in Table 9 provide answer to research question four; finding revealed the retention mean scores of experimental group male to be 58.71 with a standard deviation of 12.13 while the female students had a mean score of 56.80 with a standard deviation of 8.33. In other words, the male students retained more than their female counterparts. The result of ANCOVA as reported in Table 13 revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in the retention of male and female students taught algebra with process oriented guided inquiry learning. This is line with Marcel Papka Agah(2020) that there was no significant difference in the retention rate of students taught

Mathematics using Cooperative learning strategy and lecture method and there was no significant gender difference in the students taught mathematics using Cooperative learning strategy in the study area.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The study was to examine the effect of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) on Students' Achievement and Retention in Senior Secondary School Algebra in Bwari area council of Federal Capital Territory, FCT Abuja. The study also aimed at finding out whether process oriented guided inquiry learning had more effect on students' academic achievement and retention in algebra, also to find out whether the process oriented guided inquiry learning are gender biased in achievement and retention in algebra. The study adopted a quasi-experimental pretest post-test control group design and was carried out in two secondary schools in Bwari Area Council of FCT Abuja. Four research questions and four hypotheses were formulated to achieve the objectives of the study. Relevant literature's (theoretical framework, review of previous studies) were reviewed.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, the following conclusion could be drawn:

Process oriented guided inquiry learning was found to make students explore a wider variety of ideas needed to boost students' learning outcomes. It provides students with knowledge that can be flexibly applied (transferred) from

one problem to another and from one context to another. In other words, the approach has the principle of bring them from their world to our world, then; take them from our world back to their world so that students really get to know not only the value but also they appreciate it and most importantly they are able to actualize or practice it.

Students show higher level of retention and achieve better when taught algebra with Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning (POGIL) than conventional method this may be because teachers are released from the role of authority and to become facilitators and fellow investigators, it is an instructional approach combining guided inquiry and cooperative learning in which students are involved in the learning process. It begins with the fundamental premise that teacher is the content master while students are the content delivery master. The method is good for teaching students' algebra and is not gender biased.

Implications of Findings

The findings of the study have some implications for the mathematics teachers, students, curriculum planners and principals. Since the use of process oriented guided inquiry learning is more efficient and produces greater result than the conventional method, it seems necessary that mathematics teachers should be given adequate training on how to effectively utilize process oriented guided inquiry learning in teaching and learning.

Also, since the use of process oriented guided inquiry learning students' achievements and

retention in mathematics. It follows that curriculum planners should create the awareness on the utilization of process oriented guided inquiry learning. The findings of this study help the secondary schools' principals in planning staff development, provision for training and retraining of teachers in order to enhance process oriented guided inquiry learning for effective teaching and learning.

Limitation of the Study

This work is on the effects of Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning on the mathematics achievement and retention of secondary school students. One of the limitation is many of the students find it difficult to work as a team, finance was another limitation to the study because majority of the student do not have text book to study at home and to prepare for the lesson.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made.

1. It is therefore recommended that mathematics teachers should use process oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) to teach algebraic concepts of mathematics to both male and female students.
2. For students to achieve maximally, conventional method should not be used to teach mathematics to students at any level in secondary school education.

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3. Curriculum experts, textbook writer and workshop experts should consider including the process oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) in their future endeavors.

4. Teachers in training should train properly on how to use process oriented guided inquiry learning (POGIL) to mathematics.

Contribution to Knowledge

One major contribution of this study to knowledge is that, the results of the study have provided empirical evidence that process oriented guided inquiry learning is effective methods of teaching that enhance mathematics achievement and retention of students at secondary school level. Another contribution of this study to knowledge is that process oriented guided inquiry learning is not gender biased it can be used in either single sex school or mixed school.

Suggestions for Further Studies

The following suggestions are made for further research:

1. This study can be carried out using other secondary school subjects like Chemistry, Biology, Basic Science, Physics, etc.
2. This study can be replicated to cover other States in Nigeria or any other country of the world.
3. The study can be carried out to test two new innovative methods on the same set of students.

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Abbreviations

FCT: Federal Capital Territory

POGIL: Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Learning

SSCE: Senior Secondary Certificate Examination results

NECO: National Examination Council

WAEC: West African Examination Council

WASSCE: West African Senior School

Certificate Examination

AAT: Algebra Achievement Test

DECLARATION

We the authors hereby declare that this work is original. All references have been duly acknowledged, and cited in line with international data regulations.

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